

ANALYSIS OF LACTIC ACID CONTENT IN *LACTOBACILLI* USING WITH SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD

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Abstract. *The ability to produce lactic acid varies significantly among different strains of lactic acid bacteria. The Lactobacillus fermentum LF1 strain demonstrates the highest lactic acid production levels, making it effective for using in dairy products or other biotechnological processes. As the cultivation period increases, all strains exhibit a significant rise in lactic acid production, which is associated with the bacterial growth cycle and enhanced metabolic activity. The Lactobacillus fermentum LF1 strain is considered the most promising for commercial production of fermented products. The studied Pediococcus acidilactici 2G and Pediococcus acidilactici 1G strains also showed favorable results and have potential applications in the pharmaceutical, cosmeceutical and food industries.*

Keywords: *lactic acid bacteria, spectrophotometer, lactic acid, calibration curve.*

Currently, lactic acid is an important product with increasing demand for various industries worldwide. The global market demand for lactic acid is estimated at approximately 130–150 thousand tons per year. Lactic acid is widely used in the food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and many other industries. One of its primary production sources is the fermentation of lactose by lactic acid bacteria. Therefore, identifying suitable whey-based raw materials and optimal conditions for efficient lactic acid production is a pressing task. Lactic acid can be obtained from dairy industry by-products, particularly whey. Whey contains sufficient amounts of lactose, which can be fermented by lactic acid bacteria. For fermentation, strains of lactic acid bacteria belonging to the *Lactobacillus* genus are selected.

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) exhibit antagonistic activity against pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms, synthesizing a wide spectrum of antimicrobial compounds. Among these, lactic and acetic acids hold particular importance [Hoxha R et al., 2023]. LAB produce various antimicrobial substances, including organic acids, lactic acid, acetic acid, alcohols, diacetyl, reuterin, hydrogen peroxide, carbon dioxide, and others [L.G. Stoyanova et al., 2012]. These bacteria produce metabolites that help maintain balance with microorganisms and other organisms. The reduction in pH caused by these metabolites inhibits the growth of pathogenic microorganisms. These substances act as a protective barrier against pathogens and play a critical role in maintaining the overall homeostasis of the host environment [Aldunate M et al., 2013]. The primary metabolites include organic acids, specifically lactic and acetic acids [Vitali, B et al., 2015].

The synthesis of lactic acid by LAB has been extensively studied. For instance, in the vaginal microbiota, lactic acid lowers the vaginal pH (approximately 3.8–4.5), thereby restricting the growth of pathogens. The compounds produced by these bacteria protect the vaginal environment, preventing the colonization of *Candida* fungi and combating infections [Roberto Vazquez-Munoz et al., 2021]. Lactic acid demonstrates antimicrobial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and exhibits effects on a wide range of microscopic fungi [L.G. Stoyanova et al., 2012]. In a healthy vagina, lactic acid is the predominant organic acid, with its concentration reaching approximately 120 mM [Gajer, P et al., 2012].

The effect of *Lactobacillus crispatus* lactic acid on sexually transmitted infections, bacterial vaginosis, and vulvovaginal candidiasis (VVC), as well as its role in maintaining a healthy vaginal state, has been studied [Fuochi V et al., 2019]. The authors emphasized the use of lactic acid produced by lactobacilli in the prevention and treatment of infections caused by *Candida* fungi [Silke Baldewijns et al., 2021]. In a study, the antifungal activity of *Weissella cibaria* KM14 against *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium expansum*, and *P. oxalicum* was evaluated, revealing antifungal activity ranging from 99.4% to 94.3%. Lactic acid (13.41 g/l) was detected in the *W. cibaria* KM14 strain [Pan Liu et al., 2024]. During the research, *Lactobacillus* strains including *L.acidophilus*, *L.fermentum*, *L.brevis*, *L.plantarum*, *L.casei*, *L. delbrueckii*, and *L. jensenii* were isolated from the vaginas of both healthy and infected women. The lactic acid synthesis in these *Lactobacillus* strains was found to be 1.46 mg/l, while the maximum lactic acid level in infected patients was 1.08 mg/l [Adenike A.O. Ogunshe et al., 2011].

Optimal parameters for the lactic acid production of *Lactobacillus casei* C-1 (B-5726) were selected, including an optimal growth time of 132 hours and 5% yeast extract concentration, with cottage cheese whey as the nutrient medium. As a result, the maximum lactic acid concentration produced by *L.casei* C-1 (B-5726) culture reached 54.77 g/l [O.V. Bondareva et al., 2022]. Researchers also compared the spectrum of biologically active compounds in cultural liquids, supernatants, ultrafiltrates, and the commercial product Hilak-forte. Metabolites with protein nature were found to have concentrations of 18.5 ± 1 mg/ml in the supernatant and 18.6 ± 1 mg/ml in the cultural liquids. Additionally, lactic acid was detected in both the supernatant and cultural liquids [Yu.V. Kulakova et al., 2013].

The aim of the research is to select efficient strains that produce lactic acid and determine the optimal time for the high-level production of lactic acid by lactic acid bacteria. The results of this study will contribute to improving the economic efficiency of lactic acid production and the development of environmentally sustainable technologies.

Materials and Methods. In this method, the solution being studied is added to an iron (III) chloride solution at a concentration of 0.1–0.3%. The optical density of the resulting solution is measured at a wavelength of 380–405 nm, and the concentration of lactic acid in the initial solution is determined using a calibration curve. This method is based on the reaction between iron (III) chloride and lactate ions in the lactic acid, resulting in the formation of a yellow-green iron lactate solution.

Calibration Curve

1.2 g sample of 89% lactic acid (density = 1.2 g/cm³) was placed into a volumetric flask, and 10 ml of distilled water was added to prepare the solution.

The standard solution of lactic acid was used with the concentration of 89 g/L. The solution was diluted twice, and solutions of lactic acid were prepared with various concentrations.

In addition to preparing 0.2% ferric chloride (FeCl_3) solution, 0.3 g of hexahydrate ferric chloride salt was dissolved in a 100 ml volumetric flask with water at 25 °C. From the 0.2% FeCl_3 solution, 2 ml was taken, and 50 μl of lactic acid solution was added and mixed thoroughly. The resulting solution was measured at a wavelength of 390 nm using a 1300-SF spectrophotometer. A 0.2% FeCl_3 solution was used as the control. Subsequently, a calibration curve was drawn based on the relationship between lactic acid concentration and optical density.

Determination of Lactic Acid in the Culture Medium

To determine lactic acid, the culture medium of lactic acid bacteria was centrifuged at 5000 rpm to separate the cells. The separated cells were diluted 20 times with deionized water. From the 20-fold diluted culture medium, 50 μl was added to 2 ml of 0.2% FeCl_3 solution and mixed. The solution was measured at a wavelength of 390 nm. Experiments were conducted at room temperature (25 °C). The measured optical density was 0.628, and the lactic acid concentration was determined using the calibration curve.

The determination of lactic acid in the culture medium of lactic acid bacteria using a spectrophotometric method is an essential criterion for evaluating their lactic acid production capacity. This capacity is crucial for assessing the probiotic potential of the bacteria and their ability to inhibit the growth of pathogenic microorganisms. Measuring lactic acid levels helps evaluate the probiotic quality of the bacteria and provides insights into their metabolic properties, aiding in the assessment of their potential to combat infections.

The results of this study contribute to the exploration of bacterial probiotic properties, the development of new products, and the improvement of existing production processes.

In the calibration curve, 2 ml of 0.2% FeCl_3 solution was mixed with 50 μl of lactic acid solution. The resulting solution was measured at a wavelength of 390 nm using with 1300-SF spectrophotometer. The 0.2% FeCl_3 solution was used as the control. A calibration curve was drawn based on the relationship between optical density (D) and lactic acid concentration. Using the calibration curve, the lactic acid concentration in the culture medium was determined in mg/ml. The calculations were performed using the calibration curve, where the optical density values were plotted on the X-axis and the concentration values on the Y-axis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Calibration graph for spectrophotometric determination of lactic acid content of lactic acid bacteria.

Analysis of the results obtained.

In the study, the lactic acid production of the strains *P. acidilactici* 1G, *P. acidilactici* 2G, *L. plantarum* 3G, *L. brevis* 4G, and *L. fermentum* LF1 was determined using a spectrophotometer. The highest lactic acid production was observed on day 4 of cultivation for all strains. On day 1, *L. fermentum* LF1 produced 15.72 g/l of lactic acid, which increased significantly to 40.91 g/l by day 4. The *P. acidilactici* 2G strain produced 9.72 g/l on day 1, rising to 18.91 g/l on day 4. The lactic acid concentration of the *L. plantarum* 3G strain increased from 1.47 g/l on day 1 to 11.25 g/l on day 4. Similarly, *L. brevis* 4G showed lactic acid production increasing from 1.08 g/l on day 1 to 8.01 g/l on day 4. For *P. acidilactici* 1G, lactic acid production rose from 3.02 g/l on day 1 to 9.39 g/l on day 4.

The study results revealed that the ability of lactic acid bacteria to produce lactic acid varied significantly among the strains and depended on the duration of cultivation. The highest lactic acid-producing strain was *L. fermentum* LF1, with a lactic acid concentration reaching 40.91 g/L by day 4. In contrast, *L. plantarum* 3G was the lowest producer, with a concentration of 11.25 g/L on day 4. Both *P. acidilactici* 2G and *L. fermentum* LF1 demonstrated substantial increase in lactic acid production over the cultivation period (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Determination of lactic acid content of lactic acid bacteria

Conclusion. To conclude, spectrophotometric method allows for rapid result acquisition, enhancing efficiency in research and production processes. According to the study findings, the lactic acid production capacity of the strains is confirmed to depend on their genetic characteristics and cultivation conditions. The *Lactobacillus fermentum* LF1 strain is recommended as the most promising strain for applications in medicine, agriculture, and the food industry.

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